

D8.13 Clustering and synergies with other EU projects

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Executive summary

The Clustering and synergies with other EU projects report is written in the framework of WP8 Project Management (Task 8.5 Clustering and Interactions with Other Projects) of the MOVING Project under Grant Agreement No. 862739.

MOVING has been part of the **H2020 Rural Cluster projects** of the Rural Renaissance call (RUR-01 and RUR-02), alongside SHERPA, DESIRA, RURALIZATION, and POLIRURAL. These five projects have coordinated a common action plan, joint events, information sharing and reflections on cross-cutting issues, as well as cross-participation in activities organised by each project.

MOVING's clustering actions aimed to advance knowledge on fostering connections across cross-consortia networks, ensuring that such collaborations are more impactful than the sum of their parts, and identifying enabling and blocking factors. These links are considered very relevant to the projects' legacy.

The clustering activities have been extended to include partnerships with other projects engaged in research and innovation in mountain areas, as well as European and international initiatives related to mountains.

This deliverable highlights the various actions undertaken and other forms of result-sharing, including joint policy communication and dissemination activities and the synergies that this common work has generated.

1. Introduction

The [MOVING project](#) belonged to the **H2020 Rural Cluster projects** of the Rural Renaissance call (RUR-01 and RUR-02) together with SHERPA, DESIRA, RURALIZATION and POLIRURAL. The Rural Renaissance call's purpose was to enhance the natural, social, cultural and economic potential of rural areas and support policy coherence. The aim was to boost economic development, ecosystem services and entrepreneurial innovation by building on diversification and modernisation strategies, improving governance models, supporting innovative food and non-food value chains, and capitalising on local assets, including human natural and cultural capital. The call had the intention of renewing relevant policies dealing with rural areas and their analytical support tools. It developed synergies between the main economic sectors of rural areas, strengthened the sustainable development of food and non-food chains making use of territorial assets, supported the development of the circular economy in rural areas, developed a comprehensive approach towards digitisation as an enabler of rural economies and improved the agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS) in Europe so as to boost innovation and the delivery of the European Innovation Partnership "Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (so-called EIP-AGRI).

MOVING aimed to build capacities and develop policy frameworks across Europe to establish robust value chains that enhance the resilience and sustainability of mountain regions. The project engaged approximately 1,000 stakeholders through participatory processes at different levels, drawing on the collective intelligence of individuals from 23 mountainous regions in 11 EU Member States, three EU candidate countries (North Macedonia, Serbia, and Turkey), as well as Scotland and Switzerland. The University of Córdoba coordinated MOVING, bringing together a multi-actor and interdisciplinary consortium of 23 partner organisations¹. These partners included research centres, industry representatives, rural developers, and innovation agents from across Europe, Serbia, North Macedonia, and Turkey, reflecting the diverse characteristics of mountain areas.

The Rural Cluster aimed to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange between the projects, building on each other's activities, boosting the communication and dissemination of outcomes, and contributing to future rural policies. Deliverable 8.13 deals with the clustering activities that the project has developed with sister projects (SHERPA, DESIRA, RURALIZATION and POLIRURAL) and other relevant projects addressing related topics to MOVING. It reports the principal areas of cooperation and the joint actions in terms of clustering activities, such as cross-project cooperation, consultation and joint activities on cross-cutting issues and sharing of working methods and results, as well as joint communication and dissemination activities.

¹ MOVING project partners here: <https://www.moving-h2020.eu/partners/>

The other projects involved in this cluster are **SHERPA** (Sustainable Hub to Engage into Rural Policies with Actors), **POLIRURAL** (PoliRural Future Oriented Collaborative Policy Development for Rural Areas and People), **RURALIZATION** (The opening of rural areas to renew rural generations, jobs and farms), and **DESIRA** (Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas).

SHERPA (2019-2023) aimed to gather knowledge that contributes to the formulation of recommendations for future policies relevant to EU rural areas by creating a Science-Society-Policy interface which provides a hub for knowledge and policy. POLIRURAL (2019-2022) goal was to provide a set of knowledge resources, including an inclusive learning environment where rural populations, researchers and policymakers came together to address common problems, leaving decision-makers at different levels of government better equipped to tackle existing and emerging rural challenges, rural populations more empowered and rural areas more resilient. RURALIZATION (2019-2023) was based around the idea that a process of ‘ruralisation’ can change development patterns in rural areas, overcoming population and economic decline and generating new opportunities, and that new policy-relevant knowledge can foster a “ruralisation” process across Europe. Finally, DESIRA (2019-2023) aimed to improve the capacity of society and political bodies to respond to the challenges that digitalisation generates in agriculture, forestry and rural areas.

The clustering activities with the other projects have been a mechanism towards enhancing knowledge sharing, peer-to-peer learning and results dissemination. Some of the activities realised within this Rural Cluster have led to sharing working methodologies and results, to MOVING articles and updates published in newsletters and websites of SHERPA, DESIRA or POLIRURAL, and participating in joint events presenting outcomes and creating collaboration networks. MOVING has also disseminated its results in mountain areas beyond of Europe by partnering with major players (e.g. Euromontana, Adaptation to Altitude Network, FAO Mountain Partnership, UNIMONT, etc.).

Finally, MOVING has also established clustering relations with other research and innovation projects linked to mountain areas more recently approved, such as Horizon Europe Mount-Resilience (HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01), which objective is to support European regions and communities located in mountainous areas to increase their capacity to adapt to climate change and to transition towards a climate-resilient society, and MARGISTAR a COST action organized as a forum for knowledge synthesis, exchange, and co-creation that brings together scientists, stakeholders, and policymakers to collaboratively reflect on the challenges for sustainability in mountainous regions while moving progressively towards real-world solutions.

2. Clustering meetings

The MOVING project coordinator has maintained direct contact with the other project coordinators through joint meetings and information exchange. The five coordinators have drafted joint action plans for as long as the project timelines have overlapped. As MOVING was the last approved

project and was initiated after the pandemic break, the other projects were more advanced in their execution when the former started. However, from the beginning, an active collaboration has been developed with ongoing projects to share outcomes, and some integration meetings have been organised to go further and advance knowledge on how connections can be made across cross-consortia networks, ensuring that such collaborations are more than the sum of their parts and identify enabling and blocking factors. Project coordinators have received targeted information on the tools developed by MOVING and on the results of the project. They have also been invited to participate in dissemination events such as the EU MAP webinars and, when relevant, in study visits and training workshops.

Table 1 showcases **joint meetings and activities** organised by the projects, with the participation of members of the other projects. These activities are further described.

Table 1 Joint activities of the Rural Cluster

Activity	Type	Date	Place	MOVING contribution
Coordinators' meeting	Meeting	9 January 2020	Brussels, BE	Presentation
Coordinators' meeting	Meeting	4 March 2021	Online	Update on the action plan
Participation in the EU Rural Vision Week	Event	22-26 March 2021	Brussels, BE	Participation in the Market Place with SHERPA and DESIRA projects
SHERPA Webinar Beyond The Policy Brief: How To Engage Local Actors In The Policy Process	Webinar	2 December 2021	Online	Presentation
1st MOVING EU MAP Webinar: Mountain Value Chains: Heterogeneity and Innovation	Webinar	16 December 2021	Online	Organization and invitation to present and attend to the other projects

SHERPA Conference 2022: Make It Happen! Implementing The Rural Vision	Conference	31 January- 1 February 2022	Online	Presentation
Session on Multi-Actor Platforms and Living Labs in Rural Areas	Workshop	13-14 June 2022	Pisa, IT	Co-organiser with the SHERPA and DESIRA projects
European Society for Ecological Economics Conference 2022	Conference	14-17 June 2022	Pisa, IT	Special session on the Multi-Actor Approach with SHERPA and DESIRA projects
Writing Week	Meeting	20-24 September 2022	Evora, PT	Participation in the discussion Joint paper submitted
2nd MOVING EU MAP Webinar: European Quality schemes: the added value for mountain value chains	Webinar	8 November 2022	Online	Organization and invitation to present and attend to the other projects
RURALIZATION Final Conference	Conference	20 April 2023	Brussels, BE	Participation to the conference
SHERPA Final Conference	Conference	1-2 June 2023	Brussels, BE	Presentation in the Rural Corridor
3rd MOVING EU MAP Webinar: Protected natural sites: A constraint or an opportunity for mountain value chains?	Webinar	5 October 2023	Online	Organization and invitation to present and attend to the other projects
MOVING European foresight Workshop for resilient mountain areas	Workshop	11 January 2024	Brussels, BE	Organization and invitation to present and attend to the other projects

MOVING Scientific Conference	Conference	19-21 March 2024	Córdoba, ES	Organization and invitation to present and attend to the other projects
4th MOVING EU MAP Webinar: Towards a Policy Roadmap for vibrant mountain economies	Webinar	8 May 2024	Online	Organization and invitation to present and attend to the other projects
MOVING Final Policy Conference: A future for mountain areas in post-2027 EU priorities	Conference	13-14 June 2024	Brussels, BE	Organization and invitation to present and attend to the other projects

2.1. 1st Coordinators' meeting

On 9 January 2020, the Coordinators of SHERPA, POLIRURAL, RURALIZATION, and DESIRA organised a meeting in Brussels to draft a joint action plan. MOVING had not been initiated yet but had already been approved, and the Coordinator was invited to meet the others and present the project.

Different potential collaboration lines were analysed and included in this Action Plan, such as:

- (1) Review of rural trends, threats and opportunities
- (2) Foresight
- (3) Stakeholder engagement
- (4) Text mining
- (5) Preparation of policy brief
- (6) Communication and events
- (7) Overall coordination

Coordinators agreed to share information and outcomes from all of them.

2.2. 2nd Coordinators' meeting

On 4 March 2021, the 5 Coordinators had an online meeting to analyse the advances made since the last meeting and update the action plan. In this meeting, MOVING had already started (September 2020) but had limited progress due to the pandemic. The project's participatory nature

and Multi-Actor approach made these first months very complicated. There were several similar actions in all the projects, such as foresight analysis, but the timeline does not align with the MOVING one. In any case, the Coordinator participated in the meeting and ensured MOVING members' participation in the actions to be developed.

2.3. EU Rural Vision Week

On 22-26 March 2021, the [European Network for Rural Development \(ENRD\) organised the EU Rural Vision Week](#) in close cooperation with the European Commission. The event brought together a wide variety of rural actors and stakeholders bringing forward their views about the future of rural areas in Europe and contributing to the preparation of the Long-Term Vision for the Future of EU Rural Areas.

MOVING participated in the Market Place organised in the event, together with SHERPA and DESIRA.

2.4. SHERPA Webinar 'Beyond the Policy Brief'

On 2 December 2021, the SHERPA project organised the online session "Beyond the policy brief – How local actors engage in the policy process'. Together with other H2020 projects (LIAISON, PoliRural, SHERPA), the MOVING coordinator shared the experience and knowledge harvested through our multi-actor platforms at the local or regional levels. MOVING's contribution focused on its Community of Practice as an example of delivering local actors' opportunities to feed into the policy process at different levels, from local to European.

2.5. MOVING 1st EU MAP Webinar

On 16 December 2021, MOVING organised its [1st EU MAP Webinar "Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation"](#). The meeting aimed to present the MOVING project and publicise the EU-MAP. It showcased specific traditional or emerging value chains that focus on innovation and resilience to climate change, based on the inventory of more than 450 value chains across all European countries. Additionally, the meeting intended to enhance exchange, learning, and interaction at the EU level regarding the heterogeneity and innovation within mountain value chains. All sister projects were invited to the event, and its participation was highly valued.

2.6. SHERPA Annual Conference 2022

On 31 January and 1 February 2022, the [SHERPA Annual Conference 'Make It Happen! Implementing The Rural Vision](#) took place online. The conference was the second annual event of the project and was designed to focus on the EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas and the role of Multi-Actor Platforms in delivering it. In the group discussion on 'Farm diversification and

food chains’, [Sherman Farhad presented](#) how the MOVING project contributes to the establishment of upscaled Value Chains and to the long-term vision for rural areas (LTVRA).

2.7. Joint workshop on Multi-Actor Platforms and Living Labs in Rural Areas

On 13-14 June 2022, DESIRA, SHERPA, and MOVING held in Pisa a special session on participatory and multi-actor approaches in EU-funded projects, as a previous workshop to the European Society for Ecological Economics Conference celebrated at the University of Pisa. All these projects used this methodology, and the workshop was an opportunity to share experiences in this field and reflect on how to consolidate methods and concepts around the approach. Living Labs/Multi-Actor Platforms in rural areas are increasingly considered by innovation policies as **drivers of transformative change**. The interaction between different stakeholder groups is supposed to generate innovation adapted to the needs of users and their context, as well as to promote inclusion. The event fostered a shared reflection on the role they play and on how to improve its performance. One of the results of this event was the joint elaboration of a questionnaire to assess the role of Living Labs and Multi-Actor Platforms. The results were uploaded on an open-access platform and can be freely accessed:

Arcuri, S., Knickel, M., Brunori, G., ..., and Mattioni, D. (2023, June 19). “Living Lab questionnaire. A tool for reflecting on the experiences with Living Labs and Multi-Actor Platforms”. Retrieved from osf.io/e9ts7

2.8. European Society for Ecological Economics Conference 2022

On June 14-17, 2022, [the 14th International Conference of the European Society for Ecological Economics \(ESEE\)](#) was held in Pisa. The primary thematic areas explored included the impact of social and environmental policies, the roles of institutions and individuals in the ecological transition, resource utilisation, proposals for alternative development models (such as the post-de-growth debate and eco-feminism), and issues related to the epistemological foundations of the discipline. Several MOVING partners attended and presented project results.

2.9. Joint Writing Week

On September 20-24, 2022, a writing week was organised in Evora to explore the possibility of writing joint papers and gathering the results of the cluster projects. Due to the specificities of MOVING, based on mountain value chains, and the fact that due to the pandemic, some work had been delayed and not much data was yet available, the collaboration opportunities were limited. However, MOVING representatives participated in interesting discussions, mostly based

on methodological topics, understanding the methods used by other projects, learning from the other projects and opening options to collaborate in future actions, as will be detailed below.

As a result of this week, a join paper between DESIRA and MOVING has been drafted, and it is actually in review in Science Communication journal:

Townsend, L.; Grivins, M.; Noble, C.; Hardy, C.; Ortolani, L.; Nemes, G.; Baena-Sanz, M.; Currie, M.; Delgado-Serrano, M. (In review): *Developing digital stories in research for science communication: reflections from researchers*

2.10. MOVING 2nd EU MAP Webinar

On 8 November 2022, MOVING organised its [2nd EU MAP Webinar “European Quality schemes: the added value for mountain value chains”](#). The meeting aimed to present the MOVING project and publicise the EU-MAP. It showcased specific traditional or emerging value chains contributing to innovation and climate change resilience. Additionally, the meeting intended to enhance exchange, learning, and interaction at the EU level on the heterogeneity and innovation within mountain value chains. Branka Tome from the European Commission (DG AGRI) and Guillaume Corradino from Euromontana were invited to the meeting and provided their visions on the new EU quality policy and the implications to mountain value chains and the implementation of the optional quality term “mountain product”. All sister projects were invited to the event, and its participation was highly valued.

2.11. RURALIZATION Final Conference 2023

On 20 April 2023, [RURALIZATION hosted its Final Conference in Brussels](#). Following the project presentation, potential policies to fulfil rural dreams were analysed in a workshop. Afterwards, a "Rural Tales" session was organised, where young farmers and entrepreneurs shared their personal stories. In the conference's final session, representatives from the European Commission, researchers, and other experts discussed how specific European policies could contribute to the "ruralisation" process.

The main project outputs presented during the on-site meeting with experts and stakeholders permitted the MOVING partners that attended to incorporate some of the lessons learned over the project's four-year duration. These results are intended to help implement policies that facilitate the repopulation of rural areas, being of special interest for MOVING since depopulation and demographic changes are some of the main threats faced by mountain areas.

2.12. SHERPA Final Conference 2023

On 1-2 June 2023, the [SHERPA Final Conference](#) was held in Brussels to mark the final event of the project and present its conclusive findings to a vast set of rural actors from across Europe. As part of the conference, a Rural Corridor was organised to display innovative projects on several

aspects of rural development. The MOVING project was presented as part of the topic on “Sustainable and Resilience Value Chains”, which was discussed as one of the core thematics across the SHERPA’s lifetime.

2.13. MOVING 3rd EU MAP Webinar

On October 5 2023, MOVING organised its [3rd EU MAP Webinar “Protected natural sites: A constraint or an opportunity for mountain value chains?”](#). The objectives of the webinar were to provide an update about the Nature Restoration Law in Europe and to offer information on the protection of nature in the mountains. The session also explored the findings of a MOVING’s report: [‘Protected natural sites in MOVING regions. Implications and added value for mountain value chains.’](#) Additionally, it facilitated the exchange of knowledge, practices, and lessons learned regarding the implications of protected areas on mountain value chains. The webinar also presented the progress and results of the MOVING project and publicised the EU MAP. Kenny Meganck (IEEP), An Cliquet (University of Ghent), Roberto Aquerreta (WNMBR), Tommaso Campedelli (scientific coordinator of LIFE ShepForBio) and Stefano Sala (UNIMONT and member of Euromontana) were invited to the event to share their views on the topic. Several sister project members participated in the event.

2.14. MOVING European foresight exercise

On 11 January 2024, the [MOVING European foresight exercise](#) provided a space for experts from other EU-funded projects and initiatives to discuss the future trends impacting mountain value chains and to identify Strategic Options to address them. The goal was to draw conclusions that would support the most effective local and regional scenarios for sustainable development and resilience in mountain areas across Europe. This event was a crucial step in consolidating the results of the local foresight analyses conducted in the 23 MOVING mountain regions. It focused on benchmarking the resilience and sustainability of mountain regions and in exploring innovative approaches to ensure the long-term provision of public goods.

2.15. MOVING Scientific Conference

Between 19-21 March 2024, the [MOVING Scientific Conference](#), was held in Cordoba (Spain), inviting contributors from across Europe to present the latest scientific findings on mountain value chains. This gathering delved into the scientific results of the MOVING project for the last four years and the transformative capabilities of mountain regions and their value chains to foster resilient and sustainable futures. The event showcased a diverse range of presentations addressing environmental challenges, contributions of MOVING mountain value chains, and the promising future of mountain areas, drawing insights from across Europe.

Other leading projects on mountains were showcased during the conference. Stefano Sala from the Università della Montagna presented HE MountResilience project tackling climate change

effects in European mountain regions. Mikko Jokinen, the scientific coordinator of MARGISTAR, outlined how mountains can overcome the peripherality trap. Andrea Membretti, University of Pavia, introduced the MICLIMI project, which explores the concept of vertical migration as a strategy for adapting to climate-induced changes in the Alps.

Finally, the Director of Euromontana, Guillaume Corradino, offered his perspective on the role of European policies in mountain areas. He highlighted the years 2024-2025 as pivotal, emphasising the necessity for mountain areas to receive more significant consideration in the post-2027 CAP and Cohesion Policy, as well as in the EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas.

2.16. MOVING 4th EU MAP Webinar

On May 8 2024, MOVING organised its [4th EU MAP Webinar “Towards a Policy Roadmap for vibrant mountain economies”](#). The objectives of the meeting were to present MOVING's Strategic Options and Policy Roadmap and to provide an overview of the current discussions concerning post-2027 policy development, particularly those related to mountain and territorial development. Additionally, the meeting aimed to discuss how MOVING's Strategic Options and Policy Roadmap can be supported within the post-2027 EU policies. During the event, Silvia Nanni (DG AGRI – European Commission) made a presentation on the key achievements and ways forward for the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, and András Balazs Szechy (European Parliament Research Service) presented Post-2027 territorial development policies. Also, a round table was held, where Guillaume Corradino (Euromontana), Michael Schmitz (Council of European Municipalities and Regions) and Klaus Boele (EU Committee of the Regions, NAT Commission) gave their feedback on the MOVING Policy Roadmap.

2.17. MOVING Final Policy Conference

On 13-14 June 2014, the [MOVING Final Conference](#) was held in Brussels, marking the culmination of the project's four-year journey. The project's final results and recommendations were presented to a targeted set of stakeholders, from local to European levels, and their implications for the post-2027 EU policies were discussed. Coordinated efforts to involve participants and speakers from European institutions (DG REGIO, DG AGRI, Demography and Democracy Cabinet, EP, EESC, CoR, Joint Research Centre) and EU stakeholder organisations (Euromontana, AREPO) were made. Furthermore, the Horizon Europe MountResilience project coordinator was invited to join a round table on 'EU-wide Solutions for Rural and Mountain Regions'. This round table illustrated existing initiatives, projects and tools for increasing the resilience and sustainability of mountain value chains and mountain socio-ecological systems.

3. Other activities with the Rural Cluster

Regular exchanges and flows of information were established between projects and their respective partners of the Rural Clusters, both at communication and dissemination levels and on methodological and theoretical issues.

3.1. Communication and dissemination activities

This included regular communication and dissemination through the respective social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, website), newsletters, and project websites. MOVING's channels were used to promote relevant results and events from other projects. Similarly, communication and dissemination channels by other projects were used to share and promote MOVING's results and events to rural audiences/stakeholders and other targeted communities.

Figure 1 illustrates some examples of MOVING's Twitter account promoting relevant results and events from the Rural Cluster projects. Additionally, Figure X showcases instances of the Rural Cluster projects promoting MOVING's results and events.

Figure 1. MOVING's Twitter account and newsletter promoting updates from the Rural Cluster projects

MOVING H2020 @MOVINGH2020 · 2 may, 2022

News item about Regional recommendations from @PoliRural_H2020 project
moving-h2020.eu/news/regional-...

Learn more about this deliverable that aims to help regional teams align their action plans with the high-level missions pursued by the @EU_Commission

News item

Regional recommendations from PoliRural's project

Author: Pavel Kogut (from PoliRural Team)

Pavel Kogut y 9 más

Other EU projects

SHERPA
Recommendations for development of future rural policies (D7.3)

Desira
Policy options for an enhanced digital future

POLIRURAL
Regional recommendations from PoliRural's project (D 3.10)

Montana 174
How to access the EU Cohesion Fund as a mountain region?

MOVING H2020 @MOVINGH2020 · 12 mar, 2021

#DESIRA2020, another of our sister projects, will as well be at the #RuralVisionEU Week.

Pass by their virtual stall at the MarketPlace and find out more about the future of #digitalisation in #ruralareas!

#H2020 #HorizonEU

DESIRA_H2020 @DesiraH2020 · 12 mar, 2021

#DESIRAH2020 will be at the Rural Vision Week!

Come visit our virtual stall and learn more about the role of #digitalisation in the #RuralVisionEU

Mostrar más

DESIRA'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE LONG-TERM VISION OF RURAL AREAS

0:36

MOVING H2020 @MOVINGH2020 · 8 nov, 2021

Join #RuralizationConference2021
 EU rural initiatives and insights from research projects to promote ruralization
 Today at 1.45 to 2.15 p.m.
 With @Ruralization_EU @DesiraH2020 @ruralinterfaces @PoliRural_H2020 @newbieH2020 @MOVINGH2020

bit.ly/3CSIERT

Ruralization_H2020 @Ruralization_EU · 2 nov, 2021

#RURALIZATION Twitter Conference

Use #RuralizationConference2021 to participate in this #online event to showcase your #research to the broader audience: anyone with a #twitter account can see your presentation!👏 ...

Mostrar más

RURALIZATION TWITTER CONFERENCE

Research Generations Rural Update Policy-making

#RuralizationConference2021

@RURALIZATION_EU

Figure 2. Rural Cluster projects promoting MOVING's results and events: SHERPA's twitter account, DESIRA's twitter account and Newsletter, and Polirural Newsletter

3.2. Methodological collaboration with POLIRURAL

As a result of previous discussions in the hosted meetings, MOVING contacted the POLIRURAL Coordinator to explore the options of using some of their tools, such as the Rural Attractiveness Index and the mapping of indicators used to build it in MOVING WP5: Cross-case comparison and benchmarking. One-to-one meetings were set up with this sister project to share knowledge and experience on these specific topics. Furthermore, POLIRURAL partners participated in discussions with the WP5 partners to define MOVING thematic clusters and create typologies of Mountain Value Chains that share characteristics. Part of the outcomes of this project were used as inspiration for our WP5 work in order to perform the comparative analysis of the vulnerability, resilience and sustainability of VCs for each cluster.

4. Collaboration with other projects and organisations

Apart from the collaborations with our sister projects in the Rural Cluster, other opportunities for clustering and creating synergies were explored as follows.

4.1. Collaboration with EUROMONTANA

EUROMONTANA, the European multi-stakeholder network for sustainable development and quality of life in the mountains, is the main organization representing the interests of mountain communities at the European level. Since the project's approval, the MOVING Coordinator approached this organisation to create bridges of interaction and collaboration, offering its Director to be part of the MOVING Advisory Board.

The collaboration has proven to be very effective, and fluent communication and sharing of ideas, participation opportunities and joint work has been established. Guillaume Corradino, the Director of EUROMONTANA, has attended, in-presence or online, the different General Assemblies, organised and delivered very interesting insights and advice for the development of the project. And as showcased before, he has also participated in different events organised by MOVING.

Likewise, the MOVING Coordinator was invited to present the project at the [XII European Mountain Convention: Smart mountains](#), celebrated at Camigliatello Silano (Italy) on 25-27 October 2022. Furthermore, she will also be an invited speaker at the [XIII European Mountain Convention: Shaping the future of mountain economies](#) that will be hosted in Puigcerdá (Spain) on 15-18 October 2024, presenting the last results of MOVING.

4.2. Cluster with European and international initiatives

MOVING has built cooperation opportunities with several **European and international organisations and networks**, which act as multipliers and contribute to disseminating the project's key messages and outputs. For instance, the MOVING results, news and events were

shared through the **Rural Pact** and the **EU CAP network** respective newsletters and website. Through AEIDL, MOVING is also a member and contributor to the Rural Pact Community on Mountains, which is led by Euromontana.

MOVING also participated in the EU CAP Network Expert Group on **“Competitive and Resilience Mountain Areas”** in 2023 and 2024 through our partner HCC. The objective of this network is to gather and showcase innovative methods and inspiring success stories in capitalising on agri-food, forestry products, and other bioeconomy products. This includes addressing climate change challenges, managing land abandonment, improving the coexistence between farming and large carnivores, and exploring new opportunities like social farming and health-based agritourism.

In the framework of the Mountain Education and Innovation Manifesto, MOVING participated in the [Youth4Mountains webinar series](#) led by UNIMONT. This series aimed to promote the sharing of best practices and real-world examples of youth entrepreneurship in mountain areas across the globe. The MOVING project participated in two sessions, ‘A multifunctional approach for mountain farms’ (17 February 2022) and ‘Sharing mountain regions’ examples of innovative and sustainable tourism’ (24 March 2022).

MOVING also participated in two editions of the [ODT Forum](#) co-organised by MOVING partner ORIGIN. Indeed, our first in-person General Assembly hosted in Switzerland in October 2022 was organised in parallel with this Forum.

In 2022, the [“Women move Europe’s Mountains”](#) was produced in collaboration with Euromontana. This booklet celebrated the role of women in mountain development, a central theme for the International Mountain Day 2022.

Results and relevant news from the Rural Pact, EU CAP network and related institutional channels (DG REGIO, DG AGRI) were shared through MOVING communication channels (e.g. website, social media). MOVING results were also shared on the **Rural Pact Community Group on Mountains**, the **EU Farmbook** and the **Horizon Results Platform**.

Different content and posts on social media have been shared by organisations and institutions such as: [UNESCO Man and Biosphere](#), [EESC Agriculture Rural Development and Fisheries](#), [DG REGIO Regional & Urban Policy department of the EC](#), European Parliament [Intergroup RUMRA](#); the [European Network for Rural Development](#) (ENRD), [Euromontana](#), [Mountain Partnership](#), [Mountain Research Initiative](#), [Mountain Biodiversity](#), [EURAC Research](#), the [Centre for Mountain Studies at Perth College UHI](#), [UniMont](#), [Mountain Forum](#), [Adaptation at Altitude](#), [Europe Direct Pyrenees](#), Interreg Alpine Space as well as National Rural Networks specially from Spain, Portugal and Romania.

4.3. Clustering with new projects tackling the mountain issues

In the last years, two new projects analysing mountain areas have been approved: [Horizon Europe Mount-Resilience](#), started in September 2023 and [Cost Action MARGISTAR](#), started in 2022. The MOVING Coordinator contacted these project coordinators, and collaboration avenues were established. MARGISTAR invited the MOVING coordinator to present the project in an event they hosted in Albania on 5-6 October 2023.

Additionally, the Coordinators of both projects (Anna Giorgi from Mount-Resilience and Mikko Jokinen from MARGISTAR) were invited to be part of the Advisory Board of MOVING, and they kindly accepted, participating also in the Final MOVING Scientific and Policy Conferences.

These collaborations are considered essential for the legacy of MOVING, as both projects have shown their interest in using the methods and outcomes of the project for their future activities. Other activities developed with them are presented in Table 2.

4.4. Collaboration with members of AREPO

Our partner, A.R.E.P.O., organised the conference "[The New Legal Framework for EU Quality Products: opportunities and Challenges for Mountain and GI Products](#)" in Brussels on April 10, 2024. The event was hosted by the Committee of the Regions (CoR), under the sponsorship of Ms Karine Gloanec Maurin, the CoR rapporteur on the reform of the EU GI system.

The event was focused on the revision of the EU Geographical Indication system and was a very good opportunity to present to different policymakers and actors the main objectives and outcomes of MOVING and the analysis developed by our partners AREPO and HCC on the use of the optional quality of term 'mountain product' in the different European countries. As well as to cluster with representatives of different VCs linked to geographical indications.

4.5. Collaboration with other EU-funded projects

Synergies and joint activities with EU-funded projects beyond the Rural Cluster were pursued all along the project's lifetime. The identification of key projects was done in collaboration with the project's partners and WP1 leaders in terms of communication, dissemination, and outreach.

Table 2 presents key projects with which the MOVING project has established links.

Table 2 MOVING's Collaboration with other EU-funded projects

Project name	Focus	Means of collaboration
FEAST	Food systems transition towards healthy diets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking Meeting in May 2023
Montana174	Cohesion Policy in mountain areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • News/blog post • Newsletter promotion • Social media activity
SmartAgriHubs	Smart agricultural value chains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to workshop
MARGISTAR	European forum for the revitalization of mountain areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint meetings • Member of the MOVING Advisory Board • Participation to MOVING events • MOVING presentation at MARGISTAR's events • News/blog post • Newsletter promotion • Social media activity
MountResilience	Climate adaptation of mountain regions in Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint meetings • Member of the MOVING Advisory Board • Participation to MOVING events (Scientific Conference, Final Conference) • News/blog post • Newsletter promotion • Social media activity
GRANULAR	Rural Data for Better Rural Policies, Rural Transition, Rural Proofing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • News/blog post • Newsletter promotion • Social media activity
CODECS	Sustainable Digitalization of Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • News/blog post • Newsletter promotion • Social media activity
Tools4CAP	Methods and tools used in the Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter promotion • Social media activity

BEATLES	Climate-Smart Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint reply to public consultation on agri-food system transition • Social media activity • Newsletter promotion
RUSTIK	Rural Transition, Rural Proofing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media activity • Newsletter promotion
SMART ERA	Smart Rural Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media activity • Newsletter promotion
CLIMAAX	Climate adaptation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media activity • News/blog
Pathways2 Resilience	Climate adaptation and resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media activity • News/blog
TOP-Value EU	Mountain Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media activity • News/blog
GI-SMART	Geographical Indications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter promotion
EIDER	Rural Education for Community Empowerment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media activity • News/blog
RESIST	Regional resilience to climate change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media activity
Ruralities	Interlinking the rural spheres of Africa and the European Union	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media activity

5. Communication and dissemination activities

5.1. Website

The MOVING's website includes a dedicated webpage for [networking](#), which provides a list of Horizon and other EU-funded projects on different topics related to MOVING's field of research, including on: mountain development, rural development, value chains, mountain natural hazards, socio-ecological resilience, nature-based solutions, rural innovation and entrepreneurship. This webpage has been updated regularly throughout the project's lifetime.

The Networking webpage also provides a non-exhaustive list of European agencies, institutions and other international organisations related to the MOVING field of actions.

5.2. Social media activities

Social media is crucial for MOVING to reach its target audience. To this extent, a thoughtful communication and dissemination strategy was designed. This included a set of strategic collaborations with multiplier actors from other EU-funded projects and organisations, which were ‘recruited’ to ensure a wider outreach of the project’s results.

Synergies were created with the following projects: SHERPA, DESIRA, POLIRURAL, RURALIZATION, MountResilience, MARGISTAR, Montana174, SCALABLE, LIFE MIDMACC.

5.2.1. Newsletters

The MOVING newsletter is published twice per year, generally in June and December, and distributed through the project’s newsletter subscribers and social media followers. In the newsletter, a dedicated section is designed to include inputs from other Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects. These go from relevant events to sharing results and deliverables, as well as highlighting specific milestones or contributions to MOVING’s news and blog sections. Projects with whom MOVING by means of its newsletters has engaged are the following ones:

- SHERPA: Newsletter [December 2021](#), [June 2022](#), [June 2023](#)
- DESIRA: Newsletter [December 2021](#), [June 2022](#)
- POLIRURAL: Newsletter [June 2022](#)
- MATILDE: Newsletter [June 2023](#)
- LIFE MIDMACC: Newsletter [December 2021](#)
- PHUSICOS: Newsletter [December 2021](#)
- SCALABLE: Newsletter [June 2022](#)
- Montana174: Newsletter [June 2022](#)
- GRANULAR: Newsletter [June 2023](#)
- CODECS: Newsletter [April 2024](#)
- RUSTIK: Newsletter [June 2023](#)
- MountResilience: Newsletter [December 2023](#)
- BEATLES: Newsletter [December 2023](#)
- ESIRA: Newsletter [April 2024](#)

MARGISTAR and Horizon Europe GI-SMART will collaborate with the project in the final edition of the newsletter, scheduled for September 2024.

5.3. Delivering from the MOVING Policy Roadmap

Moving forward, and as a result of the reconvening of the European Parliament and European Commission for the 2024-2029 EU term following the June 2024 European elections, and in view of the tabling of the new EU budget and funds by July 2025 a number of actions have been and will be undertaken to maximise the impact of MOVING policy recommendations.

Following the policy roadmap validation at the MOVING Final Conference, the findings have been used by AEIDL as an expert in the Committee of the Regions Opinion on [place-based policies for the future of the EU Multi-Annual Financial Framework post 2027](#) (Rapporteur Nanette Maupertuis).

An earlier version of the Roadmap and the results of the MOVING Foresight Workshop were used by AEIDL to influence [the EESC Opinion on the Long-Term Vision for EU's Rural Areas](#), and the CoR Opinion on the [future of the Common Agricultural Policy](#).

Furthermore, the roadmap findings are a key baseline for the policy inception reports that AEIDL is preparing for the SMART ERA, FUTURAL, RURACTIVE and RURBANIVE Horizon projects on smart solutions in rural areas, which started in late 2023 and early 2024.

The final Roadmap proposals will be disseminated to the key decision-makers and institutions that contributed to the final EU MAP meeting and MOVING Final Conference, as well as the incumbent and new leadership of the European Parliament, Committee of the Regions and EESC leads, particularly on the Committees dealing with agriculture, rural development and territorial cohesion.

As the European Commission announced at the MOVING Final Conference that a public consultation on the future of the Common Agricultural Policy and possibly the Cohesion Policy would take place in December 2024, AEIDL and other MOVING partners will use the MOVING Policy Roadmap to contribute to shaping post-2027 EU policies aimed at supporting the sustainable and resilient development of mountain areas.